

**ENTREPRENEURIAL SKILLS DEVELOPMENT THROUGH
COMMUNITY THEATRE IN OGAJI COMMUNITY
THEATRE, ANKPA LGA, KOGI STATE**

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Abstract

Community Theatre's efforts in engendering transformation especially in the 21st century has consistently focused on addressing socio-political and cultural issues, and its scope has not expanded to meet or address global economic concerns in tandem with the Millennium Development Goals (MDGs), and the Nigerian Government's drive for entrepreneurship education. In this regard, the central aim of this study is hinged on discussing the potency of community theatre in building entrepreneurial skills in the rural areas. The paper adopts qualitative research methodology in its data gathering and analysis. Through Robert Chambers ideas on Participatory Development Theory and John Dewey's Experiential Learning Theory, findings show that, the participatory nature of community theatre is capable of involving the rural dwellers in a 'hands-on' learning experience process, whereby, through play, local entrepreneurs and intending entrepreneurs can learn skills to enhance productivity and innovation. The paper therefore recommends that applying the theories - which encompasses the traditional nuances of participation and communication; performance-oriented approach to build entrepreneurial skills would enhance sustainable development in the society. The study concludes that

community theatre's ability to engender development is all encompassing and not only relegated to addressing socio-political and cultural issues, but can also be employed to build entrepreneurial skills in the rural areas.

Keywords: Theatre, Community, Community Theatre, Rural Areas, Entrepreneurial Skills.

Introduction

The growing call and demands for entrepreneurship all over the world cannot be overstated. It is now the most sought after alternative in the discussion surrounding unemployment in most postcolonial epistemic discourse. Okoli and Allahna explicates on the foregoing that, "today, the level of poverty, the rise in unemployment rate, and the inability of the governments to meet the expectations of their people have reinforced the need for more emphasis on entrepreneurship across the globe especially in developing countries" (252).

However, entrepreneurial skills development cannot be discussed without a clear road map towards the impartation and development of those skills especially in the rural areas of Nigeria. This is because, the Nigerian Government's major efforts at entrepreneurial skills development has assumed a selective orientation, with the introduction of Entrepreneurship Development Studies (EDS) in the tertiary institutions, an idea that operates with the aim of teaching undergraduate entrepreneurial skills development. This research argues that, such selective orientation isolates the rural populace from enjoying the entrepreneurial skills development. In that regard, this research proposed a paradigmatic approach towards entrepreneurial skills development in the rural areas through the instrumentality of community theatre.

It is no longer in doubt that the community theatre praxis innately possesses the capacity to drive development goals in the rural areas. It advocates a fundamental re-examination of the power dynamics in societies. It also mandates a corrective and social change perspective in its praxis and projects. Most community theatre projects seek to undo the long, hidden and deep-rooted injustices that people suffer daily through no fault of their own. Although it is a comprehensive art form that provides entertainment and communal cohesion, the main driver of the praxis is societal transformation. It creates a democratic platform that acts as a laboratory for future aspirations, where one showcases how one would negotiate future eventualities. Indeed, the unspoken rule behind all community theatre experiences is the need to build individual and communal agency.

In Africa, community theatre practice serves both the academic and non-academic fields. Within the academic realm, it exposes students to the conceptual and theoretical aspect of community theatre, while the non-academic aspect of it is the

use of community theatre for social, cultural, religious and economic empowerment. In this regard, community theatre becomes a part of the people's way of life, and the aesthetics are replete in African performance experiences. One of the enduring reasons for the popularity of community theatre in rural Africa is inspired by concepts of inclusivity, community, empowerment and enablement of the poor and marginalized to take control over their own lives. In line with the foregoing, this research, through the Ogaji community theatre project at Ankpa, LGA, proposes an approach to community theatre practice which aligns with the global drive for entrepreneurial skills development with an aim to address global economic concerns in tandem with the Nigerian Government's drive for entrepreneurship education.

Statement of the Problem

Community theatre practice in Kogi East, especially in Kogi State College of Education (KSCOE), Ankpa functions as an all-encompassing genre, laced with an inclusive approach to performance, research and development aimed at educating the people, encouraging and enabling discourse in the performance arena. However, community theatre practice in KSCOE has not been employed to address or advance the drive for entrepreneurial skills development for economic growth and sustainability. It is for this reason that; this research is conceived along with a practical community theatre project at Ogaji in Ankpa, LGA, Kogi State aimed at entrepreneurial skills development in the rural areas.

Research Methodology

Through an ethnographic approach of qualitative research, the study advances a new approach to community theatre project which inspires entrepreneurial skills development in Ogaji community of Ankpa Local Government Area of Kogi East. Data collection was conducted through participant observation, open-ended and unstructured interview. Additionally, Visual Image/Video (VID) method of data collection was also employed. The data gathered was utilized to develop improvisational skit that showcases the essential skills identified through the research. The skit served as a tool for knowledge translation and dissemination, enabling community members and rural entrepreneurs to engage with and internalize the entrepreneurial skills and concepts.

Theoretical Framework

Robert Chambers ideas on Participatory Development Theory and John Dewey's Experiential Learning Theory forms the spine on which this research is hinged. Participatory development is broadly understood as an active involvement of people in making decisions about implementation of processes, programs and projects that affect them. The basic element of participatory development is to view

the term participation as the exercise of people's power in thinking and acting, and controlling their action in a collaborative framework. Accordingly, the key concept of participatory development includes the collaborative effort of people, taking initiatives by themselves in terms of their own thinking and deliberations. The main tenet of participatory community development approaches is that, "all stakeholders collaborate in any development activities from the very beginning of project identification, prioritization, planning, implementing, evaluation and monitoring. It is also geared towards achieving a sense of ownership and sustainability of the projects" (Chambers, 94). In contrast to the traditional community development approach, the participatory approach gives a greater emphasis on building capacity, empowerment, self-reliance and sustainability of the projects.

John Dewey's theory of experiential learning is grounded in the idea that education should be a process of active and dynamic engagement with the world. Dewey believed that learning is most effective when students are directly involved in their own learning experiences. Traditional education often focused on rote memorization and passive absorption of information, however, John Dewey, a prominent American philosopher, advocated for "a more dynamic and engaging approach to learning. Dewey's experiential learning theory emphasizes the importance of experience as the foundation for acquiring knowledge and skills" (Rajeev Ranjan, 17).

John Dewey's Theory of Experiential Learning remains profoundly relevant in the 21st-century educational landscape. Its emphasis on active, hands-on learning coordinated perfectly with the needs of today's students, who must face the challenges of an increasingly complex and interconnected world. Dewey's approach prepares students to "tackle real-world challenges with creativity and confidence by developing critical thinking, problem-solving, and collaborative skills. John Dewey's focus on democratic education and community involvement helps cultivate informed, engaged citizens who are equipped to contribute positively to society" (Ranjan, 8). We observe that in an era where adaptability and lifelong learning are paramount, Dewey's insights provide a learning framework for developing resilient, curious, and capable learners.

Adopting both participatory development theory and experiential learning theory can provide a comprehensive framework for entrepreneurial skills development. By integrating these approaches, the researchers can create a practical setting that encourages active engagement, experimentation, and continuous learning. This blended approach can help entrepreneurs develop a holistic set of skills from opportunity identification to venture creation, and foster a culture of innovation and economic growth.

Concept of Community Theatre

Community Theatre has been defined severally by different scholars and practitioners of theatre. It is sometimes called Participatory Theatre, Theatre for (Integrated) Development, Popular Theatre, or the People's Theatre. It is a theatre that is run by the local people of a given community, with or without the aid of outside facilitators. This is why Ayakoroma defines community theatre as "the theatre of the people, by the people, for the people" (45). In line with that, Oga Steve Abah defines Tfd as "a means of articulation by ordinary people to discuss their predicament" (245). In the same vein, Onogu agrees thus:

Community theatre is that genre of theatre that seeks to recognize and mobilize rural populace to become aware of their potentials and capabilities in addressing and finding solutions to their developmental problems. In doing so, the praxis uses the culture and practices of the people which include indigenous language idioms and other art form of expressions. Largely, community theatre strives to empower the people by leaving the means of artistic creation in their hands as tools for liberation (190).

The community theatre approach provides a unique platform for the expression and articulation of community sentiments, concerns, and ideas. By engaging community members in a collaborative and participatory process, this theatre modality facilitates the distillation of collective views into a dramatic performance that showcases practical solutions and suggestions for addressing community challenges. This creative and inclusive process enables the exploration of new development opportunities and avenues for community empowerment and growth. In line with the foregoing, Boehm & Boehm infer that:

Community theatre serves the principles of empowerment on the personal, group and community levels. Community theatre operates according to a non-directive and reflective approach, as the social worker and director work together with the participants/actors in all stages of the production, relying on the talents and skills of the participants in order to stage the play. The participants/actors take an active part in coping directly with their situation by expressing the voice of the theatre group in the local community and outside of it (286).

In almost all cases where community theatre is in existence, it is led by a team of experts who work with various organizations, community heads or 'village level workers' – like doctors, nurses, etc., assisting them to get their messages delivered to members of the community using entertainment and fun. Because of this 'all inclusive' policy of the community theatre practice, community members,

regardless of gender, age, literacy level, economic, religious or social status have a say in the overall making and production of community theatre.

Concept of Entrepreneurship Skills.

Entrepreneurship skills are business skills which an individual acquires to enable him to function effectively in the turbulent business environment as an entrepreneur. It is also the abilities and competencies required to successfully start, manage, and grow a business venture. These skills are essential for entrepreneurs to navigate the complexities of the business environment and achieve their goals. Amadi & Chuku add that, “the acquisition of entrepreneurial skills means combining personal characteristics, and financial resources within one's environment and taking advantage of them for a rewarding outcome” (59-67). Entrepreneurship skill “develops in the individual skills such as creativeness, self-independence, inventiveness and action orientation” (Anorue & Madu, 200).

Agbonifoh, defines entrepreneurship skills as “skills relating to identifying business opportunities and receiving a sustainable income from these opportunities” (72). Similarly, Folahan & Omoriyi deduce that, “entrepreneurship skills are business skills which an individual acquires to enable him to function effectively in a turbulent business environment as an entrepreneur” (60). Davidson & Honig maintains that, entrepreneurship skills development is “a programme of human capital development and a requirement for instilling and preserving an entrepreneurial ambience in an economy” (301). In this vein, Umunadi positions that, “entrepreneurship skills are business opportunity skills and creativity skills which an individual acquired personally to function effectively as an entrepreneur and be self-reliant” (132).

This research believes that, when these entrepreneurial skills are adequately put into use, the possibility of the existing small and medium-scale business venture to prosper over time will be highly effective and can sustain the owner for a long period of time, thereby contributing to government revenue and employability.

Entrepreneurial Skills Development at Ogaji Community Theatre

The Ogaji community theatre under the auspices of the Kogi State College of Education (KSCOE), Ankpa officially began on Monday, 16th of February, 2026 and ended on Saturday, 21st of February, 2026. Following the template of community theatre, preliminary visits to the community's traditional, religious, youth, women leader, vigilantes, etc, were conducted by a team of lecturers in the department led by the Head of Department, Mr. Ali, Umar Ojodale, and a few students of the department. The primary aim of the visits was to establish relationships, announce intentions, build trust, ensure relevance and ultimately to foster collaboration. After all the necessary permission were obtained, the team

approached the principal of St. Charles College Ankpa, a community school in the area to make a formal request for accommodation and performance space. Before the team made the request, they intimated the principal of their intent to work with young people in the community so that together they would analyze issues that affect them and find recommend ways of tackling them.

With all the permissions granted in line with the methodological framework of community theatre, the team embarked on community mapping. After community mapping, the next point for the community mobilization work was collection of data. The team employed the flooding method for data collection. After several days of data collection, validation of data was done in conjunction with community members. From the perspective of the community members, the identified problems were listed according to their level of impact as follows:

1. Bad Road caused by erosion.
2. Absence of Electricity for over ten years.
3. High rate of unemployment. Students were divided into three groups to begin scenario formation on the identified problems.

In the formation of scenarios, group 3 was tasked with working on the problem of unemployment. Entrepreneurial skill development for economic gain was suggested as the reprieve for unemployment. Of the list of entrepreneurial skills showcased through the first improvisational skit, the community members settled for the following skills:

1. Bead making skill
2. Tailoring skill

The next step required dividing the members of the group 3 into two different groups to enable each of the groups to begin scenario formation. The researchers reminded each of the groups that the story that would form the backdrop of the scenarios has to be relatable because it fosters connection and empathy with the audience, encourages reflection and dialogue, validates community experiences and voices, and ultimately translates to increase in engagement and participation.

Following scenario development, casting process was undertaken, and selected volunteers along with the students of KSCOE initiated rehearsals. intensive rehearsals ensued, allowing the groups to refine the concept and solidify the narrative. Over the course of several days, groups rehearsals facilitated clarification and crystallization of the idea, ultimately achieving comprehensive composition and visualization. During the rehearsals, so much was achieved; songs were learnt and integrated in the process, the cast developed songs in line with the theme of the sketch. This same period, the songs developed were fully perfected and integrated. After the songs rehearsal, the dramatic sketches were built-up through

improvisational method. The next phase saw the skeletal blockings emanating from the improvised sketches leading to production and post production discussions.

Bead Making Skill

Four participants volunteered in the group for bead making skill. Beadwork was described as resulting from appending beads to each other by joining them with a needle and a string or sewing the beads to a bit of material. The bead-making craftsmanship can be earned through formal, casual instruction or apprenticeship. Splendor cited in Adebisi, Bashorun, Abdulkadir et al, explained that, “one of the most lucrative cottage businesses to begin with extremely low capitals is beaded jewelry making. The individual can master this craft and be helpful during relaxation time or connect on it as a full-time venture to earn some income. This individual involves in entrepreneurship and thus becomes an entrepreneur” (23)

The scenario for bead making was weaved around a relatable story in the community. It is the story of the Aunt of one of the volunteers. The story is about a woman (Aunty Joy) who had gone in search of a white collar job in the city. To be able to secure the job, the employer demanded sex from her, which she vehemently declined. Frustrated and tired from seeking for a white collar job, Aunty Joy approached one of her friends who is a food vendor in the city for advice. The friend, concerned about Joy’s plight, advised her to learn bead making from a popular bead maker in the city. Aunty Joy, heeding to her friend’s advice learned bead making and became successful. the lead character of the story, Aunty Joy was played by Ejigbo, Betty Omanyo who is also a niece to Aunty Joy.

Plate 1

Plate 2

Plate 3

Plates 1, 2, and 3 show the participants during the formation of storyline. Plate 1 shows the lady asking for a job in an office, plates 2 and 3, show the lady returns to her friend to intimate her of her frustration.

Plate 4: Shows Aunty Joy as she begins the process of learning bead.

Ejigbo, Betty Omanyo, through the participatory nature of community theatre took her time for four days teaching members of her groups the rudiments of bead making. Sufficient items were procured so that each member of the bead making group can effectively participate by also doing in the process. One of the participants, Callista E. Ekele revealed that:

I used to think that to make bead is hard. It is not hard. It wasn't just like, I'm listening to instructions, and just recognizing that it can be done. But it's listening and really doing it because you had such a short amount of time, because we're changing from game-to exercise-to rehearsal. To really comprehend what was going to happen, you really had to listen to what's going to happen now. And then also, with the things that Betty were saying and demonstrating during the rehearsal, you knew she was going to say it once at that rehearsal. And you really have to take it in. And whilst you're listening to it, you can also react to it? So, I think it is, whilst you're listening, you're already interpreting it, and doing it. And it felt good, because, it gave me instant satisfaction. (*oral interview, 2026*)

Another participant, Shaibu Emmanuel remarked that:

The thing is that sometimes when I have to take a task, I feel stressed. And I feel like I have to do it perfectly. So, at the beginning of the bead making process, I was feeling stressed because I wanted to do it perfectly. I needed that period of learning, like, observe other people first, in order to kind of like, do it, better, but better in a sense that I'm not making a fool of myself, I'm actually doing the bead correctly, whatever correctly means for the team leader. (*oral interview, 2026*)

The above discussions reveal that, learning as a first-time participant in a project like this could be hard and challenging. Because of the unexpected and sudden nature of the learning process. However, it is glaring through the above interview that, approaches to learning matter. Through play and hands on experience, some nervous participants get to settle and enjoy the process of learning rather than consider it a master/student relationship. Community theatre, through its participatory nature, coupled with the hands on learning process can truly enhance skill acquisition in the rural areas.

Tailoring Skill

Ogaji community theatre practice Ankpa also had tailoring skills as part of the desired skills to be learnt by some of the participants. Eight (8) participants

indicated interest in learning tailoring skills. When these eight made their choice, it was difficult to process and adopt as part of the skills to be learnt through the participatory and experiential learning process, because, no sewing machine was brought to camp, and the Head of Department revealed that, it will be impossible to take eight sewing machines belonging to the institution out of the school into the field without obtaining the necessary permission. And, it will be practically impossible to take eight sewing machines away from the school to the camp without raising eyebrows. Due to these limitations, tailoring skills should be scrapped. While we were on the subject of scrapping off the tailoring skills, the researcher prevailed on the Head of Department to obtain permission for just a single detachable sewing machine for the sake of demonstrating to the team members, and while taking turns, team members can experience the process of sewing and stitching fabrics.

Fortunately, the school gave approval for one of the detachable sewing machines to be moved to the camp. The difficulty associated with securing more sewing machines for hands-on experience frustrated some members of the group into joining other groups. However, only four members remained to the end.

The insistence on the detachable sewing machine is informed by fact that, it can function as a mobile money-making machine, just like the ones the Hausa traders carry about, and it can also be used as an immobile money making machine, just as in a shop setting. Whichever way, the choice is left for the budding entrepreneurs to decide.

In the scenario for tailoring skills development, concerted effort was channeled into keeping the story short and crisp, because, the end point is to ensure that, the volunteers have adequate time to listen to instructions on ways to use the machine while also participating in the practical use of the said machine. The scene for the rehearsal depicts a young boy moving from street to street, compound to compound with his sewing machine on his head, calling out to anyone that might need his services. As he passes along, residents and other passersby calls for his service, thereby enabling him to make some money for himself. Some of these residents uses him as a model of dignity in labor as opposed to some of their children and wards who are depicted to be lazy and unproductive.

Plate 5: Destiny instructing members of the tailoring group while one of the researchers watches.

As noted earlier, out of the eight initial volunteers, four settled for the tailoring skills development primarily due to the inability to secure more than one sewing machine for the practical. This poses a greater challenge at the level of experiential learning. However, the challenge was better managed by scheduling the participants into pairs and allotting time for rehearsals and practice. the goal was to enable everyone to have a shot at the hands on experience, even if it was only but the basics. Below is the designed schedule for the participants.

Date	Rehearsal Time	Participants	Instructor	Duration
18/2/2026	10am – 12pm	John Stephen/Abah Aaron	Mr. Musa Yunusa	2hrs
	3pm – 5pm	Musa Ahmed/Abubakar Aishat	Mr. Musa Yunusa	2hrs
19/2/2026	10am – 12pm	Abah Aaron Abubakar Aishat	Abuh Destiny	2hrs
	3pm – 5p3	John Stephen Musa Ahmed	Abuh Destiny	2hrs
20/2/2026	10am -12pm	John Stephen/ Abah Aaron Musa Ahmed/ Abubakar Aishat	Mr. Musa Yunusa Abuh Destiny	2hrs
	3pm – 5pm	Abubakar Aishat John Stephen Abah Aaron Musa Ahmed	Mr. Musa Yunusa Abuh Destiny	2hrs

Table 1.1: Schedule for Rehearsal and hands-on learning for the Tailoring group

Plate 6: Shows a rehearsal and hands-on learning with members in the group for tailoring skill.

At the practical level, the instructors kept the hands-on experience at the very basics to enable participants to understand what is been taught. These basics includes measuring, pattern making, fabric selection, cutting, sewing, finishing etc. participants were made to understand that, the skills they were getting can be applied to various niches, from fashion design to normal repairs and alterations. Therefore, becoming a tailor can contribute to local fashion, thereby preserving cultural heritage and promoting sustainability. One of the Participant, John Stephen noted that:

I didn't know what to expect. I wasn't sure that these two worlds (theatre and entrepreneurship) let's say could work together and be at the workshop together, especially saying it and doing it at the same time. I wasn't ... I mean, I had my doubts this is what I wanted to say basically. But yes, I mean, throughout the workshop I think it worked. I would say that, right now I have a really positive attitude toward these kinds of methods, instead of being of questioning (*oral interview, 2026*).

The Participant, John Stephen in the above interview expresses confidence in the method employed to teach tailoring skill.to him, transforming theory into immediate practical could be hard but the workshop cleared his doubt on that. He

concluded by saying that he has developed a really positive attitude towards these kinds of methods of learning. In a similar manner, Abubakar Aisha reports that:

Everything looks like play to me, because, there is play from the start to the finish. There is always a drama with a moral lesson why learning tailoring is good. So, that story, when always in your mind will kind of push you to do it, because, the story makes it feel alright to learn it (*oral interview, 2026*).

This Ogaji experiment only goes to show that, the combination of participatory development theory and experiential learning theory is key to mastering tailoring skills. This is because, the instrument of the community theatre when hinged on both theories allows you to apply theoretical knowledge in real-world contexts thereby, boosting retention. In this particular context, participants didn't just learn about cutting, measuring, stitching etc., they took turn doing it, using the machine needed to do it, while rehearsing it, in an atmosphere that prioritizes inclusion and equality.

Conclusion

This research focused on the use of community theatre practice in enhancing entrepreneurial skill development in the rural areas. The larger effort of this research was to contribute to the scarce existing academic investigation regarding community theatre usage in entrepreneurship education, and to explore the potential skills that can be influenced by community theatre practices. Through this research, the role of theatre as powerful intervention tool is established. As this research has shown, the arts can play both a technical role: the transfer of skills and disciplines relevant to the creation or sustainability of a business and an inspirational role: impacting upon the intrinsic and deeper motivations of entrepreneurs.

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Oral Interview

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